

Rac-3c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-143-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	10132
Vial:	75	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 143 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.5 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 8:39:26 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 9:03:49 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.890	5133250	50.38	454441
2	10.048	5056183	49.62	296929

Asy-3c (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-147-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	10132
Vial:	74	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 147 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.5 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 8:20:53 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 9:01:37 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.891	618696	4.00	54685
2	10.046	14830302	96.00	860879

Asy-3c (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-147-3-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	54	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 147 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.5 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 7:44:21 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 9:33:02 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.880	371434	3.54	32261
2	10.030	10108783	96.46	590286